

LOW COST EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM FOR ROBOTICS, USING OPEN-SOURCE 3D PRINTERS AND OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE

Carlos García-Saura¹,
Dr. Juan González-Gómez²

¹ Escuela Politécnica Superior,
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (SPAIN)

² Robotics and Cybernetics Group,
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (SPAIN)

2012/11/19

Robots in education

Interdisciplinary field:

- **Mechanics**
- **Electronics**
- **Programming**

Platform requirements:

- **Low cost**
- **Easy to repair**
- **Flexible and expandable**

Type of platform

Commercial

vs

Custom

**Low cost? Easy to repair? Flexible and expandable?
Industrial? Home-made?**

Printbots

Build process:

Open-source 3D printer

Electronics,
motors, sensors

Plastic parts

Printbot

- Custom
- As simple as required
- Mass producible

- **Open-Source design**
 - **Shared by the community**
- [www.thingiverse.com... etc](http://www.thingiverse.com...)

Evolution and diversification

Fast growing open-hardware ecosystem!

Robotics introductory course

- 20 engineering students
- 15 hours (5 days)
- Robotics and Mechatronics group (UAM Madrid)

Our first design

Available resources:

- Arduino boards
- Motors and wheels
- Simple PCB etching

ArduSkybot Summer Workshop

- 4 primary students
- 10 hours (4 days)
- Palo Alto, California (USA)

The ArduSkyBot

- **Various sensors/actuators**
- **Simple assembly**
- **Based on the MiniSkybot and the HKTR-9000**
- **Designed in one week**
- **Four robots ready in record time!**

Printbots are great!

**This design approach
will work with any kind of
robotics course**

Conclusions/Discussion

Using printbots simplifies setting up robotic courses:

- **Small setup effort**
- **Custom platform**
- **Fast robot replication**
- **Low cost**
- **Use of available resources**
- **New way of technological education**

Questions are welcome

Thanks for your attention!

Carlos García-Saura¹,
Dr. Juan González-Gómez²

More information:

¹ <http://www.carlogsgs.es>

² <http://www.iearobotics.com>

2012/11/19